

Presentation: Késia Decoté

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music as an invitation: explorations on experiencing music together

Keywords: music performance, audience participation, liveness, online concert

The postdoctoral research project "music as an invitation" (May 2023 - June 2025) explored strategies for creative participation of audiences in online concerts. The project had the aim to examine how the affective/relational dimension of the participatory process could make an impact on the sense of liveness, i.e. 'the feeling of always being connected to other people' (Auslander 2008: 111) in the experience of online concerts. In the first year of the project, groups of women were invited to participate in online workshops to create a collaborative online concert (which had its YouTube premiere in April 2024). The second year of the project had the online participation of teenage girls in the development of a collaborative piece commissioned to composer Alwynne Pritchard, which was premiered in a live streamed concert in March 2025. Among others, these explorations unraveled new perspectives about the varied dynamics of participatory works. If different groups may call for different methods for creative process, what is the affective dimension involved in the artist/researcher's response to these calls for empathy and adjustment? Also, as the pianist (in the sense of the virtuoso soloist) start to vanish in the fabric of collaboration, here emerges the role of the piano performance as a catalyst for experiences of togetherness in music.

This presentation will draw reflections from the explorations of the music as an invitation project, illustrated by glimpses on the creative processes which took place during these two years.

Artistic/academic references

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In 2020, when the concert halls were closed because of the coronavirus pandemic, like many other musicians, I started doing online concerts.

In those times, when we could not gather people at the same place, it was really valuable being able to share music with my audience even if remotely.

Building from those first experiences, we could see that online concerts can indeed bring interesting possibilities. For example, they can reach further audiences, and they allow multimedia explorations.

Hecate writes

Format of presentation: Digital

Length of presentation: 10 minutes

About Késia

Késia Decoté is a Brazilian pianist specialising in contemporary music and in interdisciplinary practices. Késia has been developing a diverse career performing as a soloist, improviser, and chamber musician, with concerts and premieres in Brazil, Europe and Canada.

Késia is interested in exploring innovative ways to present piano music, looking for creating unique and deeply immersive artistic experiences for her audience.

Késia's debut solo album 'Para a frente' (released by Nonclassical in November 2020) features piano and toy piano works dedicated to her by emerging UK-based composers.

Késia is also committed to promoting works by women composers. She has toured the UK with Illuminate Women's Music, and is an ambassador for DONNE UK - Women in Music.

Késia holds a PhD in Arts & Music and MA (Distinction) from Oxford Brookes University, Masters Degree and Undergraduate (Cum laude) in Piano from the federal university of Rio de Janeiro. Késia is a Marie Słodowska-Curie postdoctoral fellow at the University of Bergen developing the project 'music as an invitation', which explores new forms of participation of women and girls in classical music performances.

<https://musicasaninvitation.com>

<https://kesiadecote.wordpress.com>

Photo: